

Scaling Clinical Judgment Items using Polytomous and Super- Polytomous Models

William Muntean, VUE

Joe Betts, VUE

Doyoung Kim, NCSBN

Natalie Jorion, VUE

Overview

- Model selection
- Pre-test design considerations
- Item vs person anchoring
- Item performance:
 - Psychometric
 - Content
- Scaling item sets

Polytomous Model Selection

- Categorical model considerations
 - Relationship between score categories?
- Force monotonic relationship?
 - Cumulative category models

Graded Response Model

Score Categories:
0, 1, 2, 3, 4

Polytomous Model Selection

- Categorical model considerations
 - Relationship between score categories?
- Force monotonic relationship?
 - Cumulative category models
- No assumptions about category orderings?
 - Category reference models

Nominal Response Model

Score Categories:
0, 1, 2, 3, 4

Polytomous Model Selection

- Categorical model considerations
 - Relationship between score categories?
- Force monotonic relationship?
 - Cumulative category models
- No assumptions about category orderings?
 - Category reference models
- Pair-wise ordered relationships?
 - Adjacent category models

Partial Credit Model

Score Categories:
0, 1, 2, 3, 4

Polytomous Model Selection

- Theory driven selection
 - Strength of monotonicity assumption
- Empirical / Model driven selection
 - Compare model fits between models
 - Nested models -> Likelihood ratio tests
 - Non-nested models -> Global fit indices, sufficing models

Partial Credit Model

- Anticipate monotonic relationship between points and latent ability
 - Wanted to visually inspect violations -> misfitting items?
- Good balance of stability and flexibility
 - Lower and higher thresholds

Pretesting / Calibration / Scaling Designs

- (Un) Motivated examinees
 - Examinee motivation impacts item parameters
 - (Non) Linear shift?
 - Trap questions?
 - Check for motivational factors?
- Candidate filtering
 - Mitigate artifacts contaminating item properties
 - Effective for item calibrations and scaling?

Pretesting / Calibration / Scaling Designs

- 20 Forms
 - 10 KN items
 - 12 CJ items (2 item sets)
- Linked forms
 - ~50% overlap with other forms for both KN and CJ items
- Total:
 - 40 KN items
 - 60 CJ items

Pretesting / Calibration / Scaling Designs

- Differences in item and person anchoring
 - Proxy for motivation
- Item Anchoring
 - 40% of items anchored (i.e., KN items)
- Person Anchoring
 - > 1600 examinee responses per item

Item Drift in Field Test

- Recalibrations have a strong correspondence with anchor values
 - Slope of 0.97 logits
- Mean drift of 0.16 logits
 - Field test appears more difficult

Drift

Item vs Person Anchoring

- Strong correspondence between methods
 - Slope of 1.13 logits
- Person anchoring: Mean difficulty increased by 0.32 logits

Mean Calibrated Difficulty

Item Category Curves

Item Stats

Item Stats

Item Stats

I134073.1

Item Stats

I134073.1

Information

Item Stats

1134073.1

Score Category — 0 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4

Score Category — 0 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — Total Info

Item Stats

I134073.1

Score Category — 0 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4

Score Category — 0 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — Total Info

Item Stats

I134073.1

Score Category — 0 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4

Score Category — 0 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — Total Info

Feedback for Content Developers

- Most frequently occurring option combinations
 - Mean examinee ability for each combination
 - Number of examinee's per each response combination

Cumulative Data Items: JUL17 to OCT18

Methods	N	Average of					Average Cor Item-
		RTs	Average Difficulty	Average Infit	Average Outfit	Average Cor Item-Theta	Total
CR	9	137.47	2.02	1.28	1.60	0.14	0.28
DD_Cloze	35	56.97	-0.58	1.16	1.27	0.18	0.30
DD_Ration	2	175.49	0.11	1.00	1.00	0.39	0.50
DD_Table	11	110.03	-0.49	1.42	1.45	0.21	0.38
DND_Bow	3	149.78	0.31	1.56	1.99	0.35	0.58
DND_Cloze	1	83.46	-1.32	1.12	1.19	0.21	0.35
DND_Fixed	46	93.14	-0.01	1.23	1.30	0.24	0.37
DND_Free	31	59.04	-0.89	1.19	1.22	0.17	0.34
DND_MR	96	73.75	0.48	1.18	1.25	0.18	0.38
DND_Ration	5	134.49	0.94	1.16	1.21	0.26	0.37
HL_Table	14	80.38	0.84	1.24	1.35	0.17	0.32
HL_Text	55	75.88	1.07	1.25	1.43	0.15	0.32
Matrix_MC	65	75.04	-0.29	1.34	1.35	0.22	0.42
Matrix_MR	14	66.47	0.13	1.44	1.51	0.26	0.49
MC	261	37.92	0.05	1.04	1.07	0.16	0.20
MR	192	65.18	0.25	1.28	1.42	0.17	0.34
MULTI	35	109.50	0.51	1.50	1.74	0.22	0.46
OR	9	104.59	2.53	1.01	1.04	0.11	0.16
Grand Total	884	65.03	0.18	1.20	1.29	0.18	0.31

Item sets

I134090.1

I134091.1

I134092.1

I134093.1

I134094.1

I134095.1

Item sets: Super-polytomous scaling

- Aggregating item scores
 - Scaling to PCM allows item sets to span across entire latent scale
- Item dependencies
 - Mathematically accounts for any item dependencies
 - Testlet model yielded small effects
 - Content provides opportunity for correcting poor judgment
 - Content written on well-known topics

Cumulative Data Scenarios: JUL17 to OCT18

Scenario Types	N	Av. N per form	Av. Points	Min Points	Max Points	Av. Difficulty	SD Difficulty	Av. Infit	Av. Outfit	Av. Corr w/ Final Theta	Av. Corr w/ CJ form w/o Score
CJ_Free	47	4,303	17.83	8	27	0.12	0.28	1.92	2.30	0.33	0.23
CJ_Task_01	20	1,112	25.10	17	38	-0.08	0.27	2.08	2.12	0.40	0.29
Grand Total	67	3,351	20.00	8	38	0.06	0.29	1.96	2.25	0.35	0.25

Conclusions

- Model selection:
 - Depends on strength of assumptions
 - Simplicity/Flexibility tradeoffs
- Item Performance:
 - Visual inspection on item characteristics and item descriptives
 - Option inspection from content developers
- Item sets:
 - Aggregating points across individual items removes dependencies
 - Scaling to PCM allows item sets to span across entire latent scale
- Pre-test designs:
 - Reduce the number of unmotivated examinees
 - Item vs Person anchoring can lead to different levels of calibrated difficulties

Thanks!